

CULTURAL SCIENCES

SEMIOTICS AND FILM LANGUAGE IN KAZAKH AND KOREAN CINEMA

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Abstract

The current state of Kazakh cinema, Korean cinema, the importance of the film language in the movies of the two countries, the development of Kazakh and Korean web series.

Keywords: *semiotics, film language, Kazakh and Korean cinema.*

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“Cinema is life. Only life without boring moments”

A. Hitchcock

In the life of a modern person of any culture, cinema occupies an important place, because cinema is one of those worlds in which everyone gets what he needs, in the genre of his choice, he can go on a fantasy or space journey, even on the most sensual or a historical event that his inner needs and desires require. All this can be called the magic of cinema and the power of cinema. And behind this power is work that the average viewer does not know – we are talking about the work of the scriptwriter and director, the selection of stage set, the work of actors with hundreds of people on the set, further editing, writing or selecting music by genre and the last moment to reach the audience is a demonstration of the movie, the achievement of audience enthusiasm. In a word, this is an amazing world of cinema.

It is known that not everyone is familiar with the fact that cinema has its own movie language or cinematic semiotics, only the screenwriter of the movie or the soundtrack to the movie knows about this, and no one else knows about it except them. Cinematic semiotics was first introduced into the world of science and cinema by the scientist Yu. M. Lotman. Cinematic language refers to everything from the style of filmmaking chosen by the director to the costumes chosen by the operator, the lighting, the artist, and even the actors. Because each of them has a movie language or movie semiotics. As for the original movie, the production mentions the world. And during filming, thanks to the skill of the actor, you can use a lot of gestures, eye movements, facial expressions, etc. This is because in addition to the text in the movie, it is accompanied by a vague cinematic language. What is the language of cinema? Here, the question arises of what the average viewer needs. The answer is that every movie has its own semiotic features. It can be in the text, in the montage, in the operator, or in a particular tone of light. Thus, the viewer not only sees the movie, but also from the first moments of the movie learns what the it is

about, its style, and what special impression this movie makes.

According to Lotman [1], the color of each sign, each melody or ray of light, together with its features, gives a certain meaning. All these are clear signs of a language code. As humanity has changed, so has the movie industry. Cinema can tell a lot about the people of a country, its internal or external culture. Today's 21st century is dominated by postmodern cinema. Previously, cinema was a change of stage sets, then silent movies (rich in many characters), then went through the stages of sound cinema, and now it is moving into many different movie formats, such as Dolby Digital, 4K, IMAX. Thanks to this, we now see a movie with its own colorist and style of each country and people, and we know what the director or screenwriter wants to say through many celebrities.

Each film represents the world of culture not only of certain people, but also the inner and unique world of each person. Therefore, in this article, the authors tried to conduct a comparative analysis of Kazakh cinema with Korean and their role in popular web series. The purpose of the article is to review and compare the semiotics of Korean and Kazakh web series.

In recent years, Korean cinema has made a lasting impression on the world, and Netflix [2] has recorded an unprecedented amount of viewing. The name of the performance is "The Squid Game" or "The Squid Game" directed by Hwang Dong Hyuk. The series shows that the Korean people do not mind living in poverty and killing each other for money.

Let's turn our attention to the symbolic aspects of this flag, whose characters will have to go through many competitions over the course of the series. It turns out that all these competitions are children's games, but the heroes themselves decide what kind of game it is before the competition begins. Towards the end of the series, when the number of people decreases, in the room where the characters live, all kinds of games and serial numbers are displayed, which is one of the first semiotic signs. Further evidence that the director pays a lot of attention to the language of the film or any of the characters is that he appears in the same game under the character name 001. The Korean name is "Ko Il Nam", which means primary or first. During the invitation of characters to the tournament, we meet with good

symbolism, where the player is given two cards, one of which is red, and the other is green. It turns out that the character who chose the green color will participate in the competition as a player. Conversely, a character who chooses a red card shows their agreement to protect the players. It is symbolic that these two colors were not chosen by chance, because in the color scheme green and red are opposite to each other, that is, they describe the relationship between the players and the guards. Red is known to be intimidating. This is further evidence of director Hwang Dong Hook's semiotic approach to each character.

Each character shows how their life in the series ends, in the first 5 or 10 scenes, as they are now presented in the series. In other words, by introducing each character to the average viewer, he showed how he would die in that series. Obviously, this is a manifestation of the director's high symbolic knowledge. We notice the symbolism that the director introduced into the masks of the guards. The proof of this is the fact that the guards have three types of masks: round, triangular and square. It is clear that the director wanted to show the guards a group of ants. That is, for ants, everyone is engaged only in their own business and clearly knows their role. It also says that every guard must do his job. With a round mask, he plays the role of an ordinary worker. During the series, it turns out that the triangle is a soldier, and the square is a commander. The director was able to draw symbols on the stairs leading to the game. He built a staircase based on a painting by M.K. Escher "Relationships" [3], built in 1953. The viewer knows that the stairs immediately cause a feeling of fear or panic. In terms of political symbolism, it is clear from the series that there is a group of people who are sponsoring the game. Here the director wanted to show that people with pockets are ready to kill each other for money, and that sponsors have paid for it.

Alisher Utev, director of the 5:32 series on Salem Social [4], is one of the most popular series that has taken a special place among our Kazakhstani web series. 5:32 – a series about real maniacs. The very name is full of symbolism. This is because, as stated in verse 32 of Sura 5 of the Holy Qur'an [5] "he who is guilty of the death of one person has committed the murder of the whole world, and he who has saved the life of one person has saved the whole world," as stated in a private conversation by the director. In general, the semiotic point of view of the director during the series is clear from the point of view of the cinematographer and composer. The work of the cameraman B. Arginov is special, because the framing and shooting style immediately immerse the viewer in this atmosphere. Throughout the series, the operator filmed on camera without the help of a tripod and stabilizer. The goal of this technique was to give the viewer as much access to the atmosphere as possible and create the feeling of being at one with the characters. This shows the use of cinematic language between director and cinematographer.

Another feature of the series is the soundtrack written by the composer exclusively for the series. Composer R. Ziganshin [6] wrote a complete musical accompaniment to the series with the help of a guitar. It is interesting that here the viewer, through the music, fully completes the plot or the inner experiences of the actor that occur during the script. This is a job that requires great skill. In the course of the series, the investigator determines by the actions and traces of maniacs or by the style of murder what type of maniacs they belong to, which can be understood as a sign of symbolism. And the investigator shows that they have a lot to do in life. Another clear sign of the semiotic language is that in the series we often see the number 5:32, which even appears on the clock or in the character's story. The director labeled each maniac with his own characteristics and did not identify them, thereby revealing their motives or motives for the crime. We can say that this web series aroused unprecedented interest in Kazakhstan and significantly raised the level of the Kazakh web series.

In comparison, the model of these two web series has semiotics with cinematic language used in its own style on both sides, and each is not the same. Because two countries, two cultures, two styles, but they all used the symbols of the cinematic language. In addition to the main screenplay, other theories of human interest are revealed. And a person who knows the language of cinema is especially impressed. Even though Korean cinema is richer and more developed in history than Kazakh cinema, it can be said that our country's web series are at a good level. But that's still not enough to make it onto a global Netflix-like platform, and movie language plays a big part in that. We see its effect. After all, the sign can be found anywhere in life.

Thus, we found out that it was M. Lotman who first singled out and studied the semiotics of language in cinema in the form of theory and practice. Thus, we now know many new theories, such as the filmmaking process of movie critics, directors, actors and ordinary viewers, not only filming it, but also the role of the idea that accompanies it, adding symbols and meanings to it. And a special place in cinema is occupied by the symbol of movie language.

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